

Planning Research Collaboration

The Turing Way Workshop

In *The Turing Way*, we consider collaboration essential for reproducible research and provide a separate guide with best practices and recommendations for your reference.

Choose one research project that you are currently working on and get started with this worksheet!

Project Details:

Project title, affiliation, important links and stakeholders details.

Communication within the project

Preferred channels and tools, Communication norms and policies (links to documents).

Ways to Collaborate

List all opportunities for knowledge exchange such as events, meetings, 1:1 feedback, project management and task allocation processes etc.

Goals	Short-term goals	Long-term goals
Shared goals		
Personal goals		

Skills

Learn in this project:

Teach others in this project:

Uncertainties

List what you don't know about the project, what uncertainties in the project exist, how they affect your work, who can you speak about it?

Personal collaboration and development plans to share with collaborators

What would you like to share with others in your project to ensure effective collaboration and avoid possible miscommunication. Here you can also provide details on how you will seek support for personal development in what ways you might be able to help/support others.

Communicating your research outside the project (outreach)

Together with your colleagues, identify ways to communicate your research with others in your institute, in your research field and outside your research field. This may include institute's newsletter, seminars, coffee chats, conferences, publication, preprint, data repository, blogpost etc.